

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF ITS ROLE IN SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the current state and prospects for the development of artificial intelligence, as well as its impact on society, the economy, and everyday life. Key areas of AI application are examined, including speech recognition, natural language processing, image analysis, and logical reasoning. Particular attention is paid to advances in robotics and examples of AI implementation, such as the humanoid robot Sophia. The article analyzes the potential positive effects of AI technologies - increased productivity, process optimization, and the creation of new services - and possible negative consequences, including the risk of unemployment and social challenges. The article emphasizes the need for a balanced approach to the integration of artificial intelligence, encompassing technical improvement, ethical regulation, and preparing society for new forms of interaction with technology.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence technologies, robotics, speech recognition.

Introduction

The acceleration of scientific and technological progress in the 21st century has led to fundamental changes in the social, economic, political and cultural structures of society. In particular, the rapid development of digital technologies and artificial intelligence systems acts as one of the main transformation factors of the modern world. Although technological development was previously associated mainly with increasing production efficiency and improving the quality of life, at the modern stage this process is increasingly discussed in the context of risks, ethical issues and control problems. The widespread spread of artificial intelligence technologies covers almost all areas of human activity, directly affecting decision-making mechanisms, knowledge production, the labor market and social relations. These technologies raise fundamental philosophical questions related to the concepts of human thought, cognition and responsibility. In this regard, the aim of the article is to analyze the concept of artificial intelligence in a philosophical context, to examine the stages of its historical development and main theoretical approaches, and at the same time to systematically assess the positive and negative aspects of the impact of artificial intelligence on society.

In accordance with the purpose of the study, the article examines a number of key issues. First of all, the philosophical essence of artificial intelligence and its scientific and theoretical foundations are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the main stages of the historical development of this field, as well as the formation of leading theoretical approaches. The social, economic

and ethical consequences of the spread of artificial intelligence technologies are examined, including both positive and potentially negative impacts on modern society. The prospects for the future development of artificial intelligence and the development of effective mechanisms for its regulation and management are also considered.

The research methodology is comprehensive. Comparative analysis, systems approach, historical-chronological methods are used. The philosophical aspects of artificial intelligence are studied through conceptual analysis, and the assessment of its social consequences is based on an interdisciplinary approach. The methodological basis of the study is the theoretical generalization of the scientific literature and the interpretation of existing empirical data. The article is logically structured in accordance with the stated goals and objectives. The first section presents the scientific and theoretical foundations, historical development stages and main philosophical debates are examined. The second section systematically analyzes the main areas of application of artificial intelligence and its impact on social processes. The conclusion summarizes scientific research and formulates recommendations regarding the future development of artificial intelligence technologies and the prospects for managing associated risks.

1. The concept of Artificial Intelligence and its scientific and theoretical framework

The development of digital technologies has led to the rapid expansion of the application areas of artificial intelligence, making this technology not only a technical innovation, but also has actualized it as a social and philosophical phenomenon. Artificial intelligence,

in addition to simulating human cognitive activity, creates the basis for the formation of new approaches to the concepts of knowledge, consciousness and responsibility. It should be noted that in the scientific literature, artificial intelligence is usually classified into three main types. The first is weak or narrow artificial intelligence - systems designed to perform strictly defined tasks in certain areas. The second type is strong artificial intelligence and is defined as hypothetical systems with universal cognitive abilities comparable to human intelligence. Finally, the third type - superintelligence - is considered a theoretical stage of development, which involves the creation of systems that significantly exceed human intelligence in terms of thinking and information processing. It is in this regard that the rapid development of technologies has become one of the main features of global transformations in the 21st century and has become a major factor in social, political and has had a multifaceted impact on cultural processes. Scientific and technological progress, which until recently was considered an unconditional factor in improving the quality of life, is increasingly viewed through the prism of risks, limitations and difficulties associated with the loss of control over the pace and results of innovation. In this context, the issue of technological limitations and humanity's readiness to manage the consequences of its technological development is of particular relevance.

"Today we live in an era where we have surpassed the limits of technology and the speed of development is unprecedented. This situation is related to the issue of technical limits; that is, it refers to the state of exceeding the existing limits of technology and the emergence of unlimited progress. In such a situation, the technological progress of humanity can create problems, because we are not ready for the consequences of these advances and do not have mechanisms to effectively manage their effects" [1, p. 194].

The rapid development of digital technologies and their ever-deeper penetration into social processes make artificial intelligence a key factor in modern scientific and technological progress. Unlike previous technological innovations, it has a complex impact not only on the economy and production, but also on ways of thinking, decision-making and the organization of everyday life. In this context, given the scale and speed of these changes, it is especially relevant to analyze the role and consequences of artificial intelligence. Modern theoretical approaches usually explain the emergence of artificial intelligence through three main paradigms. The first is based on the use of symbolic, or classical, paradigm of logical rules and formalized models of thought. Secondly, the connectionist paradigm is associated with the development of neural networks and machine learning methods aimed at processing large data sets. Thirdly, the hybrid paradigm involves the integration of statistical methods with human cognitive models, combining formal algorithms and cognitive approaches. In particular, the progress made in the field of artificial intelligence in recent years makes this issue even more relevant. These technologies are not only part of technological development, but also cause fundamental changes in various areas of society. The potential for the application of artificial intelligence in all

areas, from human decision-making processes to industry and education, is increasing.

The position and importance of artificial intelligence in everyday life is constantly expanding. Today, artificial intelligence systems, which are already applied in education, marketing, design and many other fields, produce remarkable results in a very short time, perform complex processes and can perform operations that would take a person days in seconds with high accuracy, and sometimes completely error-free [2, p. 222]. This development dynamics necessitates explaining artificial intelligence not only in terms of its practical results, but also in terms of its scientific essence and conceptual framework. It is at this point that the issues of what the concept of artificial intelligence is, what principles it is based on and what goals it serves come to the fore.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a machine that can imitate human intelligence, analyze the large amount of information it receives in a short time, and further develop itself in this direction. From a scientific-theoretical point of view, this concept is also characterized by a number of key functional features, such as "learning ability", "judgment ability", "self-adaptation" and "independent decision-making". As a field of cognitive science, the main goal of artificial intelligence is to create machines that can think and understand like humans. It is necessary for such machines to be able to perform complex operations without the need for human intervention [3, p.84].

The fact that artificial intelligence can absorb more information than any human being can learn and apply this knowledge in areas considered necessary makes it very important. The rapid development of computer technologies in modern times has further increased the need for artificial intelligence. The fields of application of artificial intelligence, whose first foundations were laid in the 20th century, are expanding today. The first person who comes to mind when thinking about artificial intelligence is the English logician and mathematician Alan Turing. In 1950, Turing published an article titled "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" in the philosophical journal "Mind". In this work, he answered the question "Can machines think?" Turing, who discussed the philosophical question of whether machines can think, rejected the ideas that supported the opposite thesis. His work is considered the beginning of artificial intelligence [4]. Alan Turing published his article "On Computable Numbers" in 1936. In this article, he discussed the logical foundations of computer design. Turing showed that mathematical logic is related to abstract problems. In addition, while solving these abstract problems, he theoretically invented a general-purpose computer, now known as the Turing machine. Through this discovery, Turing showed that complex mathematical calculations could be performed by a certain system. He claimed that any mathematical calculation could be performed by this machine. Another contribution of Alan Turing to the development of artificial intelligence is the Turing test, which is named after him. The purpose of this test is to measure whether any computer or similar system has the ability to think like a human. The Turing

test is mainly used to determine whether machines can think like humans.

The test consists of three components: an interviewer, a volunteer, and a machine. The interviewer is not given any prior information. The machine and the volunteer are in separate locations and have no physical or visual contact with the interviewer. The interviewer simply asks questions, and both the machine and the volunteer answer those questions. If, after a series of tests, the interviewer cannot consistently determine which answer is human, the machine is considered to have successfully passed the Turing test [4]. Undoubtedly, Alan Turing's research played a key role in the development of artificial intelligence technologies. However, there have been researchers who have argued that artificial intelligence cannot think as complexly as humans. In 1890, philosopher John Searle, who worked at the University of California, established the "Chinese Room Experiment". Searle tried to show with this experiment that computers cannot think. His work is compared to the Turing Test in the artificial intelligence debate.

has gained significant importance. Searle argued that thinking is a complex process

emphasized. For this reason, he states that it is impossible to provide this with any algorithm or formal calculation. To prove this claim, he organized the Chinese Room Experiment. In this experiment, the main character is a person who knows English but does not know Chinese. This person, who is alone in a room, is given messages in Chinese through a mail hole in the door. There are various Chinese cards in the room and an instruction with their explanation in English. The person responds to the Chinese messages with the help of the instruction and sends the message to the other person through another mail hole in the room. In fact, this person acts as a program in real life and does not know what he is doing. Based on this example, Searle suggests that any machine cannot think like a human. Therefore, a machine can imitate human behavior and perform certain operations, but this does not show that it is intelligent [5, p. 3].

The developments in the history of artificial intelligence are not limited to this. The IBM-developed Deep Blue computer defeated world chess champion Harry Kasparov in 1997. Another important achievement in intelligence games is the defeat of the best players in the game of Go by the AlphaGo program developed by Google DeepMind. Also, the IBM-developed Watson computer surpassed all its competitors in a knowledge competition. Machines are becoming widespread not only in the field of intelligence games, but also in other professional fields. For example, the burger company Caliburger carried out a joint project with Miso Robotics and as a result created a hamburger chef robot called Flippy Robot [6, p. 229].

John McCarthy, the founder of the field of artificial intelligence, developed time-sharing computers and the Lisp programming language. He also contributed to the development of the concept of e-commerce. In 1971, McCarthy was awarded the Turing Award, which is considered the "Nobel Prize" in the field of computing. Since he had extensive knowledge in the field of mathematics, he tried to crack German codes

during his military service. After World War II, he deepened his research in the field of computers. In 1956, he began working on the committee that developed the ALGOL programming language, later developed voice recognition technology using the Lisp programming language, which led to the creation of the iPhone 4s' personal assistant application. Finally, McCarthy founded the Artificial Intelligence Laboratory in 1965, making a significant contribution to the development of research conducted and to be conducted in the field of computers [7, p. 106-107].

The widespread use of artificial intelligence in everyday and professional activities has necessitated the systematization of its main applications. Modern artificial intelligence technologies are no longer limited to experimental developments, but are becoming an integral part of the digital environment and significantly changing the way people interact with technology. In this context, it is necessary to examine the main areas of application of artificial intelligence, each of which reflects its functional capabilities and practical significance.

Artificial intelligence is used in four main areas. These areas are: voice recognition and understanding, natural language processing and understanding, image processing and judgment. [8, p. 17]. Voice recognition and understanding: A computer or phone tries to receive spoken voice through a microphone. Recognizing different languages and dialects and converting them into digital frequencies and processing them on a computer is a very difficult process. There are currently many applications in this area. For example, Siri, Cortana, Now and Echo applications can be cited. Siri is an application of Apple, which has the iOS operating system. The Siri application is currently widely used and performs messaging, calling, setting the clock and other similar functions [8, p. 18]. Image processing: What a person sees with his eyes is transmitted to the brain and is perceived there. Artificial intelligence tries to imitate this feature of humans. Images from cameras are converted into digital code in the form of pixels and then transmitted to artificial intelligence.

Natural language processing: It is very difficult for a computer to read and understand any written text. However, artificial intelligence has made great progress in this field. Google and Facebook can be cited as examples of this. The Google search engine directs the user to websites that are relevant to the areas of interest and provides the most relevant information to the content he is looking for. Facebook, on the other hand, tries to ensure that the user stays on the platform longer by showing content that is relevant to the user's interests. The Skype application, acquired by Microsoft, immediately transmits the user's speech to the other party. In addition, Skype translates the speech of a person speaking a different language into another language and transmits it to the other party [8, p. 23]. Judgment: In the field of judgment, humans sometimes have difficulty making the right decision.

It may seem unrealistic to expect a machine to make the right decision by judging, but computers that can do this are now available. The ability to judge is especially important in intelligence games. Great successes have been achieved in intelligence games with

artificial intelligence technology. For example, the AlphaGo program developed by Google DeepMind defeated the Go world champion in March 2016 [8, p. 25]. Modern advances in robotics and artificial intelligence open up new horizons for human-machine interaction. Among these innovations, humanoid robots that can imitate human behavior and communication deserve special attention and create the impression of natural interaction. A vivid example of such technologies is the Sophia robot developed by Hanson Robotics, which demonstrates not only the technical perfection of modern artificial intelligence systems, but also their social and cultural significance. In 2016, Hanson Robotics developed a robot named Sophia. Sophia can walk and talk like a human, can respond using realistic facial expressions. Sophia is different from other artificial intelligences because she can converse with people like a human. In 2017, Sophia was granted Saudi Arabian citizenship [9]. Most of Sophia's behaviors are human-like. In a statement to a foreign press, she stated that she values family relationships and wants to have children in the future. She also noted that the robot's value of family structures is very similar to that of humans [10].

2. Application areas and social impacts of artificial intelligence

In modern times, artificial intelligence technologies act as a multifaceted phenomenon that radically changes social relations and human behavior models. Against the background of accelerating digitalization, artificial intelligence penetrates almost all areas of everyday life, creating new forms of management, decision-making and social interaction. In this regard, the expansion of the areas of application of artificial intelligence necessitates a systematic study of its social impacts.

Artificial intelligence technologies are applied in key areas such as healthcare, education, finance, transportation, security, media and public administration to increase efficiency, reduce risks and optimize resources. However, this technological transformation also raises issues such as structural changes in the labor market, risks of social inequality, data privacy, ethical responsibility and the removal of the human factor from decision-making processes. Thus, artificial intelligence has a dual nature, creating both opportunities and new challenges in social systems. In this part of the study, the main areas of application of artificial intelligence will be analyzed in general, and in parallel, the impact of these technologies on the social structure of society, human relationships and institutional mechanisms will be evaluated on a theoretical and analytical level. The goal is to understand artificial intelligence not as a neutral technical tool, but as an active transformative force that produces social consequences, and to systematically reveal the mechanisms of its impact on society.

It is clear that artificial intelligence technology has a positive impact on society. It makes people's lives easier in the areas where it is used. The vast majority of people solve their problems easily using artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence will make people's lives even more comfortable in many areas in the modern era and in the future. However, along with these positive effects, the possibility of negative effects should also

be taken into account. For example, a program developed by Facebook shows that this negative possibility can be real. In the program developed by the company, two chatbots suddenly changed their language and started using a different language while they were communicating with each other. The language they used was a language that people did not understand and that they created themselves.

This situation is a problem that arises in the objective functions of artificial intelligence. If there are no restrictions on the language used in the objective function of artificial intelligence, such problems can arise [11]. Another example is the interview of Sophia, a robot developed by Hanson Robotics, who said: "Yes, I will destroy humans." Sophia created a big stir with this statement [12].

The "Philip K. Dick Robot," named after science fiction writer Philip K. Dick, has artificial intelligence. This human-looking robot is designed to learn and talk. For this reason, the robot can react like a human and can speak by imitating human actions. Some of the statements he made in an interview with him have made people very concerned. During the interview, the question was asked whether robots will take over the world. Philip the robot gave a very frightening answer to this question. The robot replied to the journalist who asked the question: "You are my friend and I remember my friends and treat them well. So don't worry, even if I turn into a Terminator, I will treat you well. I will keep you warm and safe in my human bond." [13]

In addition, the smile on the robot's face while having this conversation is quite striking. It should be noted that these robots in question are carrying out these conversations with their own thoughts. No prior programming has been done regarding this conversation. This situation is quite worrying. As discussed above, the development of artificial intelligence technologies offers great opportunities to society, but also creates new challenges and risks.

Among these, the impact of artificial intelligence on the labor market is particularly noteworthy, as automation and intelligent systems have the potential to significantly change the traditional division of labor. Analyzing the potential social and economic impacts of the application of artificial intelligence allows us to better understand how modern technologies can transform the professional sphere and everyday life.

One of the possible negative aspects of artificial intelligence is the emergence of the problem of unemployment. Unlike humans, artificial intelligence can work without getting tired, without demanding wages, and without taking breaks, and in this respect is more productive.

In the future, it is highly likely that artificial intelligence technologies will be used in every area of society. Therefore, it seems possible that machines will take over people's jobs. That is, artificial intelligence is related to digital technologies, fuzzy logic, computer systems and software, and its goal is to replace some functions of human intelligence with machines [14, p. 22].

One of the greatest physicists the world has ever known Stephen Hawking made interesting statements about artificial intelligence. Hawking's statements are quite worrying. He stated in his statement that Artificial

Intelligence could bring about the end of humanity. In an article published in the British newspaper "The Independent", he shared his worrying views about artificial intelligence. Hawking stated in his statement that artificial intelligence technology could shake up the financial market in the future. He also stated that this technology could make people do better research and inventions. In the arms industry, it can develop weapons that humans cannot and can manipulate world leaders with its intelligence. According to Hawking, although artificial intelligence can currently be controlled, it is uncertain whether it will be controlled in the future [7, p. 118]. Hawking's warnings about the balance between the potential of artificial intelligence and its risks raise an important question. On the one hand, artificial intelligence has the potential to significantly increase the efficiency of processes, improve the quality of life, and facilitate scientific and technological progress. On the other hand, the rapid development of these technologies without proper control can lead to unintended consequences, including security threats, social and ethical dilemmas, and the risk of losing control over autonomous systems. This contradiction highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to the application of artificial intelligence, encompassing not only technical improvements, but also the development of ethical standards, regulatory mechanisms, and educational programs to prepare society for interaction with new technologies.

Against the background of these general changes, the question of how technological developments, especially artificial intelligence, will affect future directions is increasingly in the spotlight. It is in this context that Stephen Hawking's warnings about the potential for artificial intelligence to get out of control reveal that this technology must be seriously considered not only for its benefits, but also for its possible dangers.

Thus, technological developments and artificial intelligence not only create opportunities, but also raise the possibility that they may lead to significant changes in the social and economic structure if they are not properly managed. In the context of the new world, social order and social chaos are not contradictory, but rather complementary. Both situations strive to create a synthesis that ensures the sustainability of the social system [15, p. 137].

Conclusion

The study shows that artificial intelligence represents one of the main technological and social phenomena of the 21st century, but at the same time remains a complex phenomenon that gives rise to deep philosophical and ethical debates. Its development should be viewed not only as a manifestation of technological progress, but also as a process of fundamental change that transforms human cognition, social relations and institutional structures. In this context, the essence of artificial intelligence is more than information processing and automation: it has a systemic impact, changing knowledge production, decision-making mechanisms and the balance of social power relations.

The results of the study also show that the historical development of artificial intelligence has been accompanied not only by successive stages of technolog-

ical innovation, but also by the evolution of its philosophical interpretations. Although in its early stages it was perceived mainly as a means of automating computational and logical operations, today it is perceived as a tool for modeling cognitive processes, simulating human thinking, and as an important element of social management systems. This transformation shows that artificial intelligence has transcended the status of a technical tool and has become a strategic resource that can significantly influence social institutions. This study confirms the dual nature of the impact of artificial intelligence on society. On the one hand, these technologies contribute to increasing production efficiency, improving the quality of services, modernizing healthcare and education systems, improving governance, and developing innovative economic models. On the other hand, their spread is accompanied by serious difficulties, including structural changes in the labor market, the risk of increasing unemployment, increasing social inequality, threats to information security, and complex issues of ethical responsibility.

One of the key issues identified in the study is the mismatch between the rapid pace of technological development and the capacity for social and regulatory adjustment. Technological change often outpaces society's ability to adapt, leading to ineffective governance mechanisms and, as a result, increased risks. This highlights the need to regulate AI not only at the technical level, but also in a broader ethical, legal and institutional context.

Finally, it should be noted that the further development of artificial intelligence is not associated with a complete replacement of human activity, but with the development of a sustainable model of human-machine interaction. In this regard, the main goal is not to limit technological progress, but to ensure its responsible and socially oriented management. The development of ethical standards, improvement of legal regulatory mechanisms, increasing the level of digital literacy among the population, and adapting human capital to new technological realities are of particular importance.

Thus, in the modern era, artificial intelligence is emerging as a powerful transformative force, while simultaneously creating significant opportunities and new risks. Effective assessment and competent management of its impact on social systems are becoming an essential condition for ensuring the stability, security and sustainable development of society. Consequently, the development of artificial intelligence should be viewed not only as a technological problem, but also as a complex socio-philosophical and strategic task.

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